

Correlation Analysis of Effective Factors in Attracting Customers to a New Product of a Brand

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to get a deeper understanding of the severity of affecting factors on the attraction of customers from the new product of a TAK MAKARON products in Bandar Abbas city, the Republic of Islamic Republic of Iran. The study influencing factors to attract customers are: products quality, products availability, good prices, packaging design and advertising, which are obtained after in-depth review of library resources.

Data for this study were collected by using the qualitative research method. The information was gathered from the literature, articles and by interviewing. The interviews were based on the questionnaire. The theoretical framework in this paper aimed to the study the main elements of marketing communication and customer relationships marketing. Also, Kendall tau rank correlation coefficient has been used to determine the correlation. This was done by using SPSS statistical software.

The results of this study indicate the correlation of all variables with customer attraction, although the percentage of these factors is different in attracting customers.

Keywords: Marketing Communication, Customer Attraction, Customer Selection, Customer Relationship

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Customer Relationship Marketing

“Customer relationship marketing is a strategy which is designed to promote short-term customer loyalty, communications and actions. Customer Relationship Marketing approach is focused on customer retention more than on customer acquisition. It is designed to develop long-term and strong connection between an organization and customers by providing them information which is suitable for their needs and wants and by promoting open communications.”

Customer Relationship Marketing is the creation and development of long-term profitable and interactive relationships with existing customers and potential ones, suppliers, various interest groups, etc., so that the commitment is common and profitable for both parties. When the company is oriented to the customers, there are some principles which are called “the golden rules of customer-oriented organizations”, such as:

1. The needs and the wants of the customers are the starting point for all activities.
2. The company always seeks feedback from the customers.
3. The products are strictly adopted to the needs of the customers.
4. The company monitors the activities of its competitors at all times.
5. “You may not serve all customers in the same way, but they can all be treated with the same respect”.

6. The customer is King.

7. The company respects its staff and organizes the staff as being the most important company resource.

8. Company tries to get regular customers through after-sales marketing.

These rules must be a company's everyday activity. According to these rules, a company cannot compromise its management with customers and staff, but can pay for something else.

1.1.1. Basic Model of Customer Relationship Marketing

There are different kinds of customers of all ages and attitudes, and the educational backgrounds, occupations and income levels are different as well, so it is very important to remember that there is a need for a realistic marketing model.

In the model, which is described below, marketing is seen as an objective oriented decision-making process. This process proceeds as the customer relationship develops. There are different types of relationships between a company and customer. In the situation when the customer is a potential customer who has never heard about the company before, a customer relationship has not even begun. The rest are existing customers. Some of them can be regular ones, and another group is called “chance” customers, who buy the company's products occasionally.

Customers are divided into different groups according to their stage in the customer relationship. The basic model of customer relationship marketing is presented in Figure 1.

Marketing Objective	Establishing the Relationship	Developing the Relationship
Marketing Target Group	Potential Customers	Existing Customers
Marketing Orientation Forms	Mass Marketing	
	Interactive Marketing	
	Internal Marketing	

Figure 1: The basic model of customer relationship marketing (Lahtinen & Isoviita 1994)

According to Figure 1, there are two different groups of customers. The first one is potential customers, where potential purchases can be selected for target groups of the market. And the second one is existing customers, which includes those customers who have purchased company's products at least once, and some regular clients.

The first target of Customer Relationship Marketing is to create customer relationships and the second one is to develop these customer relationships. The size and composition of the target group depends on the purpose and follows the marketing objectives. That is why objectives must change with customer moves. The objectives and target groups of customer relationship marketing are: establishing customer relationship (the stage of getting customers), and developing customer relationship (the stage of keeping the customers). In the first stage of establishing the target group there are segments chosen from potential customers. The second stage of developing deals with the target group of existing customers, who are divided into three groups of experimenters, chance customers, and regular customers.

A company markets differently to a customer who knows nothing about the company than it markets to the knowledgeable regular customer. The marketing methods are called marketing operation forms. Each operation uses a different marketing mix (product, price, place, promotion, relationship network, customer service). Marketing operation forms include:

1. Internal marketing:

- the ways through which the company's own personnel will be generally better motivated in its work and especially in customer oriented activities;
- the ways through which company's management improves the working

atmosphere, the education of the personnel, information services and its own management behavior;

- Internally weak organizations cannot be strong externally – the success of internal marketing is the basis for the rest of the marketing operations.

2. Mass marketing

- external marketing, which aims to build a customer relationship, is mainly directed at large groups;
- the ways through which potential customers become interested in the company and its products and purchase for the first time;
- Marketing strategies are the 4 P's of traditional mass marketing (product, price, place, and promotion)

3. Interactive marketing

- the use of personal or other alternative interactive methods in a
- sales or service situations in order to create and develop a customer
- relationship which aims to:
 - Attract the interest of potential customers to the company and its products
 - Convert the chance customers into regular customers
 - Engage the regular customers in the custom and encourage them to spread the news about the company's products to potential customers.

1.1.2. Goals of Customer Relationship Marketing

The goals of Customer Relationship Marketing can help companies and provide the data for marketers to overcome internal barriers and set right marketing goals, which lead to the increasing of the profit and company success in the market. There are five main goals for Customer Relationship Marketing:

- 1) Defining and identifying the most strategically important prospects/clients. Mostly, companies concentrate on the clients who they used to be focused on, but they do not think about what kind of customers, there should be now and in the future. Defining and identifying the best potential clients for the growth of the company is one of the main goals of the organization.
- 2) Acquiring the most strategically important prospects/clients. This goal is a traditional one in organizations and its initiatives, include differentiation, positioning, and branding, client added-value events, advertising, direct mail,

publishing, speaking engagements, and numerous communications tactics. Moreover, this goal is important for business developers, who arrange appointments with prospects and clients.

- 3) Retaining the most strategically important prospects/clients. By using the applications and internal marketing environment, the organization can strengthen its infrastructure to manage customer relationships.
- 4) Increasing the firm's amount of revenue by its most strategically important current client. This means that the organization should grow its revenues by the best clients it has, while its competitors will not do that. Now companies developed innovative solution to meet their client's emerging need, while simply doing the communication more with current and stable clients. So, the organization must focus more on the functions and develop strategies to serve prioritized customers.
- 5) Increasing the perceived value of the firm to all audiences (including suppliers and employees). This goal will help the company to encompass public relations, media relations, and internal marketing tactics. If the company has not yet identified its priority clients, the company's image and presentation of its products/services can be directed to the wrong audience.

1.2. Marketing communication

All organizations, including large and small ones, commercial, government, educational and other organizations, need to communicate with a variety of participants. It could be getting materials and services for the business activities, or cooperating with others to protect a suitable distribution of goods and services. Marketing communication is a management process through which an organization engages with its various audiences. So, the main idea of marketing communication is in its promotion of the organization and its offerings. It identifies the role which the organization plays in the marketing process and effects the factors which can have the audiences.

There are many different consumers, who have a variety of products and services to choose from. Marketing communication provides a main activity to get understanding the purposes of interested parties and appreciation of value of goods and services, which are offered those parties.

1.2.1. Marketing communication tools

There are five main marketing communication tools or disciplines, including advertising, sales promotion,

personal selling, public relations and publicity, and direct marketing. In addition, there is a media, which delivers a message to target audience, where the time and space can be bought by an organization. Organizations have developed innovative combinations of promotional mix to reach the audiences successfully. Promotional mix has shifted original emphases from mass communication campaigns to more direct and highly targeted promotional activities by using direct marketing and other tools of the marketing communication mix. Through-the-line and below the-line communications are used much more these days, but in Figure 2 it is seen that these elements are brought together.

Figure 2. Above-the-line and below-the-line communications (Blythe 2009).

i. Advertising

Advertising is an audio or visual form of marketing communication that employs an openly sponsored, non-personal message to promote or sell a product, service or idea. The main feature of advertising is to increase awareness. It is a complex form of communication with thousands of variations to get a message to the customers.

There are eight ways of advertising, including print advertising, guerrilla advertising, broadcast, outdoor, public service, product placement, cell phone and mobile and online advertising (digital).

ii. Sales promotion

Sales promotion is the term used to describe short-term incentives offered to customers with the intention of increasing sales in the immediate future. It is used to introduce a new product, clear out inventories, attract traffic flow, and to lift sales. It is more connected to consumer markets, rather than to B2B markets, because business buyers are less influenced by short-term promotions, or sales promotions do not suit long-term relations. The need for promoting a product or service arises from the competition between organizations. Sellers must attract customers and their attention somehow. The information, which is needed to attract customers takes the form of advertising the

availability of something. Incentives are introduced like discounts; expressive applications are displays and shows, and low prices.

Sales promotion must provide customer incentives; they cost money, but they must produce additional volume to pay for the expenses. Sales promotion must be carefully regulated to realize the purpose. Holding promotions will teach customers to buy in effect of the promotion, when the avoiding of promotions will let rivals to pull customers away.

The company can introduce many types of sales promotion activities including free sampling, coupons, discounts, premiums, product demonstrations, point-of purchase (POP) materials, and refunds.

iii. Personal Selling

“Personal selling is the interactive process whereby a buyer and a seller negotiate an exchange process. It is usually, though not necessarily, carried out in a face-to-face encounter between the parties.”

To be successful in personal sales the sales person must know and understand how to sell the particular product to the needs of a customer. The sales person controls the whole process of sales, and must be influencing, but not aggressive and pushing. The seller must present the benefits of the product in a way that motivates the buyer to make a purchase. There are five main objectives in personal selling:

1. Building product awareness, where a sales person instructs and informs buyers of new product offerings.
2. Creating interest, where the selling person must create a face-to-face contact with the customer to get to experience the product or service for the first time, which builds product awareness.
3. Providing information is a large part of the selling process and in the conversations as well, where the seller focuses on the product information.
4. Stimulating demand is the main objective in influencing the buyer to make a purchase.
5. Reinforcing a brand helps to build strong relations and create regular communication with customers.

iv. Public Relations

Public relations (PR) are the “planned and sustained effort to establish and maintain goodwill and mutual understanding between an organization and its publics”. In another words, PR is the way the organizations and individuals communicate with the media and public. It communicates to the target audience directly or indirectly by using media. The main goal of this communications is to create strong relations between organizations and audience and to

maintain a positive image. There are PR organizations, which help companies to create and maintain a good reputation, in order to make a strong relationship with the customers, which increases sales.

There are used some tools for PR specialists and companies for maintaining relationships with target customers. To do that they use news releases and statements to media, bulletins, organization and public events, and conventions, for example.

v. Direct marketing

Direct marketing is an interactive marketing system that, using one or several advertising media, results in a measurable response or change at any sales outlets. There are two ways of direct marketing with the message from the selling person to the customer and customer’s feedback of seller’s made work. Direct marketing has a certain method.

This method is based on the communication and distribution channels and making those channels shorter and effective. The purpose of this method is to save the costs of the company and to manage good work of the communication and distribution channels without intermediaries. So, there are two different methods of direct marketing, including personal direct selling and “instrumental” direct selling.

Personal direct selling (calling and visiting customers) is when the organization sells the products or services to the customers face-to-face or by phone without using any media. “Instrumental” direct selling (mail-order selling) is a case when orders are placed without any intermediaries, but by mail-order catalogues, coupons advertisements, and advertisements letters with order cards, membership magazines, videotext and superteltext. In the case of some expensive goods and industrial products, instrumental and personal communication methods are combined.

2. MATERIALS & METHODS

2.1. Case Research Tak Makaron

Tak Makaron Co. began its activities in 1994 which was the first time a continuous method production line has become operational in Iran. It produces about 40 different types of pasta with the high quality semolina flour in compliance with GMP & HACCP regulations. At present by utilizing 6 pasta production lines from Buhler (Switzerland) and Fava (Italy) companies, the plant is capable to produce more than 450 tons of various products per day. The unique product quality, high nutritive value and attractive packaging with competitive price have all added different countries to the group as Tak Makaron's consumers.

The plant has recently turned to producing new products such as sesame oil, flour, cake and so on.

2.2. Study Location

This study was conducted in tow shopping centers in Bandar Abbas City. Shopping centers include: Refah Shopping Center and TARA Hyper Markets.

2.3. Population and Sample

Data were collected through a questionnaire that was implemented in person through interviews with 600 consumers to randomly chosen ages 20 to 65 at the place where they buy Tak Makaron products and asking them how much research variables have been effective in attracting them to new Tak Makaron products? The sample was calculated according to the Cochran formula.

N = Statistical population size = 680,366

Z = Confidence Level= 95%

p = Ratio of a trait in the population = 50%

q = Percentage of those without that trait in the population (q = 1-p)

d = Acceptable margin of error = 5%

n = Sample size = 384

3. Result and discussion

This study aimed to identify the severity of affecting factors on customers' attraction when a brand delivers a new product to the market and determines the correlation of those factors with customer attraction.

The influencing factors on customer attraction based on library studies are: products quality, products availability, good prices, packaging design and advertising.

By reviewing Table 1, the following results can be extracted:

- 1) The majority of customers think that the products quality is very important, 59%, important for 32%, less important for 5% and not important at all only for 4%.
- 2) The products availability is very important for 24% of the customers, important for 42%, less important for 18% and not important at all for 16%.
- 3) 31% of costumes think that good price is very important, for the majority of the customers, good price is important, 48% thinks that it is important, less important for 12% and, again, 9% think that it is not important at all.
- 4) The packaging design is very important for 13% of customers, important for 40.5%, less important for 36% and not important at all for 10.5%.
- 5) As regards the advertising, 37.5% of people answered that it is very important, 41.5% think that it is important, less important for 19% and not important at all for 2%.

Furthermore, the Kendall's tau findings, describes the significant correlation between all the research variables and customer attraction (Table2)

Table 1. Frequency Distribution of Reasons for Attracting Customers to a New Product

	<i>Not Important</i>	<i>Less Important</i>	<i>Important</i>	<i>Very Important</i>
Advertising	2%	19%	41.5%	37.5%
Good Price	9%	12%	48%	31%
Packaging Design	10.5%	36%	40.5%	13%
Products Availability	16%	18%	42%	24%
Products Quality	4%	5%	32%	59%

Table 2. An Overview of Kendall's tau Correlation Coefficient between Research Variables and Customer Attraction to a New Product

	<i>Advertising</i>		<i>Good Price</i>		<i>Packaging Design</i>		<i>Products Availability</i>		<i>Products Quality</i>	
Customer Attraction	-0.41	0.77*	0.73*	0.52	-.027	0.61*	0.004	0.73*	-0.40	0.93*

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed).

6. CONCLUSIONS

Brands (companies) can rely on the CRM, as well as utilizing communication tools to create a constructive interaction with customers. It highlights the importance of having a good customer relationship management and also, importance of how to use communication tools. Addressing these issues lead to the introduction of new products to customers at the right time and in a more favorable way, which ultimately attracting customers to buy.

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